

Innovative learning environments and the digital era: Finding space for mathematics identity

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The dichotomy of traditional versus reform mathematics classrooms has been of much research interest, including how students and teachers perform agentic identities in these contexts. Nowadays, however, mathematics learning in Aotearoa New Zealand plays out on a stage that may be a vast departure from either of these classrooms. So called “innovative learning environments” are characterised by fluid seating arrangements, multiple teachers, many digital devices; and they may be predominantly ‘online’. In fact, we might argue that mathematics instruction today is ‘device-centred’ more than being teacher- or student-centred, a trend exacerbated by distance-learning during the pandemic. How then do teachers and students develop mathematics identities in this new era? A performative definition for identity allows us to see identity more easily as existing outside the individual; not only produced in and by social contexts, but also in wider societal narratives. In this paper I will discuss how ‘innovative’ learning environments are situated in neoliberal ideology and “twenty-first century” discourses, and I consider the production of teacher and learner identity scripts in these spaces.

Setting the scene

Let me start by painting a picture of a primary classroom in Aotearoa New Zealand. First you must delete your image of four walls, a desk for each child, and a forward-facing orientation. The floor plan of this classroom is hexagonal – an irregular polygon that would fit three or more traditional classroom squares. There are sectioned off spaces or smaller rooms with walls of glass. The furniture is varied and optional; children may sit on the floor, on cushions, on beanbags, at low tables, at higher tables, or they may stand or even lie down. Their belongings are in ‘tote trays’ so that they are mobile. The devices are mobile as well – children may bring their own laptops, Chromebooks, or tablets/I-pads; and the classroom also has its own collection of these for the children to use. There are multiple teachers but they may not be easy to spot, not being situated front and centre. I suspect for some it will be difficult to reconcile this scene with a more traditional image of the mathematics classroom that would otherwise automatically spring to mind. I invite you to click on the link below and watch the short video titled “Understanding pedagogy” (from: Te Kete Ipurangi (TKI): Ministry of Education, 2021).

<https://www.inclusive.tki.org.nz/guides/planning-innovative-learning-environments-iles/>

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The scene above does not describe *every* classroom in Aotearoa New Zealand, there is certainly a great deal of variety in classroom types, however it (and the embedded video) represent the direction taken in designing educational contexts over the past decade. Let us call these examples the “new” classroom, in order to differentiate and acknowledge that there are certainly other, more traditional classrooms to be found elsewhere throughout the country.

Of course, I have described a pre-pandemic classroom. Even after the return from lockdowns and emergency remote teaching it was certainly inappropriate to have such a high level of interaction between children and free movement through the space. On the other hand, the use of digital technologies that were already prevalent has increased. In Aotearoa New Zealand we are fortunate to have returned (at the time of writing) to ‘normal’ classroom interaction, but there remains the question of what is normal, or what might be the new normal? As Borba and colleagues suggest, the pandemic may entirely change the agenda for mathematics education (Borba, 2021; Engelbrecht et al., 2020). However, we have already seen how crises may be harnessed as a rationale for wide-scale educational change (Mutch, 2017; Williamson, Eynon & Potter, 2020), and I suspect it is safe to assume that these technology-rich, innovative learning spaces, such as seen in the link above, will become increasingly common, at least in Aotearoa New Zealand.

One might ask what *mathematics* teaching and learning look like in the ‘new’ classroom space. Whilst it seems clear that the ‘new’ classroom is a vast departure from the traditional classrooms of last century, my question is not whether the innovation constitutes an improvement to mathematics teaching and learning, rather, I am interested in how these environments (including online environments) produce identities as teachers and learners of mathematics. This is an important question given the value of identity research in understanding teacher change (e.g., Chronaki & Matos, 2013; Lutovac & Kaasila, 2017) and students’ relationships with and participation in mathematics (e.g., Mendick, Moreau, & Epstein, 2009; Radovic, Black, Salas, & Williams, 2017).

In this paper I first outline a definition of identity as performative, following Judith Butler’s work on gender identity. I extend her theatrical metaphor to propose a method by which we may more easily understand identity as beyond the individual, and produced by the wider socio-cultural and political context. Next, I will briefly give an account of the historical, educational context of Aotearoa New Zealand – the ‘theatre’. Then I will discuss the ‘stage’ for learning mathematics (and producing identity), in this case innovative learning environments (ILEs) that include online programs for mathematics instruction, as I term the ‘new’ classroom. The discussion is based on my current research into the phenomenon of learning mathematics via online instructional programs and my personal observations of ILE classroom spaces. Additionally, in lieu of data, I invite you to consider the video linked above, and also the website for *Mathletics* (3P Learning, 2021, <https://www.mathletics.com/nz>), both of which I will refer to throughout.

Performative identity and extending the theatre metaphor

A few years ago, Darinka Radovic and I were invited to write a definition for mathematics learner identity for the *Encyclopedia of Mathematics Education* (Lerman, 2020). We were tasked to give a definition that *reflected* (rather than advanced) the work on identity in mathematics education currently. We finally settled on the following:

A socially produced way of being, as enacted and recognized in relation to learning mathematics. It involves stories, discourses and actions, decisions, and affiliations that people use to construct who they are in relation to mathematics, but also in interaction with multiple other simultaneously lived identities. This incorporates how they are treated and seen by others, how the local practice is defined and what social discourses are drawn upon regarding mathematics and the self. (Darragh & Radovic, 2018, para. 1)

Although the above definition focuses on mathematics learner identity, a mathematics teacher identity may be thought of in a similar way. We aimed to write a definition that encompassed the various ways that mathematics learner identity is defined and operationalised in the discipline. Each aspect: (e.g., socially produced, enacted, recognized, multiple) is evident in the wider literature, but each of these aspects may be understood slightly differently depending on the perspective taken. There are certainly many ways to understand identity, and sometimes definitions are vague or absent altogether in literature published in the field. Elsewhere we have both argued that authors must be explicit in the way they define and operationalise identity for the purpose of their research (Darragh, 2016; Radovic, Black, Williams, & Salas, 2018), and so I will attempt to be explicit here. I take a *performative* view of mathematics identity, drawn from Butler (1988), that explains the social production of identity acts and highlights the role of recognition as part of identity. Others in mathematics education have seen value in Butler's work for identity (e.g., Chronaki, 2011; de Freitas, 2008; Gholson & Martin, 2019; Mendick, 2017); I find it useful myself because it allows an operationalisation of identity that incorporates more than interview narratives, and focuses the gaze beyond the individual to look at identity enactment and the production of identity within various layers of context. This enables a more thorough understanding of the relationships people form with mathematics learning and teaching and of the decisions they make regarding future participation in higher education or engagement with professional learning.

Judith Butler defines *gender* identity as performative, that is, a “stylised repetition of acts” (Butler, 1988, p. 519). Butler argues “a body becomes its gender through a series of acts which are renewed, revised, and consolidated through time”; thus identity is not predetermined but rather “the legacy of sedimented acts” (p. 523). I find it very useful to consider mathematics learner or teacher identity in the same way, that is, a series of acts which are renewed, revised, and consolidated over time. Butler wrote this particular definition in the '*Theatre Journal*', which may explain the theatrical emphasis on the idea of an 'act'; however, it is worth noting the theatre metaphor has generated some confusion as it tends to imply a separation between the actor and the act, as opposed to a poststructuralist understanding of

subjectivity where the act produces the actor (Jagger, 2008), which is key to performativity. Yet, I see much potential in exploiting the theatre metaphor in order to make explicit the wider social and political context in which identities are performed and performatively produced. We may consider the socio-political context to be the *theatre* and the immediate social context (e.g. the classroom) as the *stage*. We might ask ourselves what the typical *scripts* or normative ways of being are, and whether *improvisations* are possible. Finally, the *audience* takes up the important role of recognising (and validating) identity performances. I contend that understanding how identity is performatively produced requires a consideration of the wider temporal, ideological, and physical contexts.

I would like to unpack and operationalise this theatrical metaphor as I consider how the ‘new’ classroom context produces mathematics identity. I invite you to contemplate this metaphor alongside me as you view the linked video, the website from one popular online mathematics instructional program, *Mathletics* (3P Learning, 2021); or you may like to reflect on your own context. First of all, I situate us within the wider socio-political context of Aotearoa New Zealand’s neoliberal educational system.

The ‘theatre’: Socio-political-historical context of education in Aotearoa New Zealand

In Aotearoa New Zealand, like many other countries around the world, neoliberal policies have dominated the political scene over the past three decades thus impacting the education system considerably (Ladd & Fiske, 2003; McMaster, 2013). Neoliberalism is an economic and political ideology that proposes individual, entrepreneurial freedom and is characterised by free markets (Harvey, 2005). Some of the ways we see neoliberalism at work in education is the devolution of control from central government to individual schools; ‘free choice’ for parents in where they send their children to school; voucher systems where the money follows the student; and outsourcing of educational provision to private providers (Thrupp, O’Neill, Powell, & Butler, 2020). Although an early adopter of neoliberal education, Aotearoa New Zealand has resisted some of the policies that have become entrenched in other nation’s educational systems (McMaster, 2013). However, some neoliberal features that remain are: devolution of governance and curriculum to local schools (Lange, 1988; Ministry of Education, 2007; O’Neill, 2011), and private providers being allowed to make profit in public schools via educational provision of particular subject areas, including mathematics (Thrupp et al., 2020).

The beginning of neoliberalism within education for Aotearoa New Zealand was the policy document “Tomorrow’s Schools” (Lange, 1988). *Tomorrow’s Schools* devolved much responsibility for education to individual schools, managed by ‘Boards of Trustees’, which were made up of parents in the community. One intention of the policy was to give greater voice to parents and the community (McMaster, 2013). This allowed a great deal of autonomy to individual schools and, together with the 1991 abolition of school enrolment zones,

encouraged school choice and competition for students (Ladd & Fiske, 2003; McMaster, 2013). Curriculum reform swiftly followed, with new curricula in 1992, and again in 2007. The 2007 curriculum is remarkable for the small size of the document. All eight content areas and all 13 years of schooling are contained in a document of only 65 pages, of which mathematics has no more than 10 pages (Ministry of Education, 2007). In other words, the national curriculum contains only a list of achievement objectives without guidelines of how to teach them. The impetus was given to schools to create their own localised curriculum based on this document. On one hand this meant schools were able to cater educational experiences to the local community's wants and needs (see also McMurchy-Pilkington, Trinick, & Meaney, 2013). On the other hand, some schools struggled to develop a curriculum that was sufficient for the needs of their students. In either case, the variety of different practices in schools has increased under this policy.

Another prominent feature of the 2007 curriculum is the focus on producing “twenty-first century learners” (Benade, 2015; Ministry of Education, 2007). This is a global movement, driven in part by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), which has questioned “‘outmoded’ transmission models of teaching” and called for reform of educational systems (Benade, 2019, p. 58; see also OECD, 2013). In Aotearoa New Zealand this “transformation is increasingly evident in new technology-rich flexible learning environments, characterised by large open spaces, permeable boundaries and diverse furnishings emphasising student comfort, health and flexibility” (Benade, 2019, p. 58). Benade also notes that the design reflects the “neoliberal concern with ensuring that education is relevant to the realities of the twenty-first century workplace” (Benade, 2017, pp. 804–805), as shall be elaborated further later.

A more recent event that had a significant impact on schooling in Aotearoa New Zealand was the 2010 earthquake in Christchurch. The disaster was used as a justification for widespread permanent closure of some schools, to the devastation and surprise of their local communities (Mutch, 2017). With the post-earthquake re-building of schools, many were designed using “Innovative Learning Environment” (ILE) guidelines – with classroom spaces as described in the opening paragraphs. Subsequently, all school builds, expansions, and renovations in the entire country have been required to follow the ILE design in order to receive funding (Bradbeer et al., 2017). The ILE space certainly looks innovative and modern, but it has been criticised for not being based on research evidence (Bradbeer et al., 2017), motivated either by lower cost or neoliberal ideology, and evidence of the way a crisis can be harnessed by politics for educational change (Mutch, 2017). Over the past decade this has meant many schools have realigned their classrooms to the ILE model, although others remain traditionally ‘single cell’.

Within this neoliberal and ‘technology rich’ context, mathematics education has increasingly drawn on digital technologies as a regular part of instruction. A recent OECD survey found that children in Aotearoa had the fastest growing rate of computer use in mathematics classes in the OECD with 89% of students using this technology as part of their

mathematics learning (Vincent-Lancrin, Urgel, Kar, & Jacotin, 2019). With such high availability of the technology, it is hardly surprising that the majority of schools have turned to commercial programs to provide instructional material using these computers and mobile devices. As many as 80% of primary schools in Aotearoa New Zealand subscribe to at least one online mathematics instructional program (OMIP), such as *Mathletics*, *Study Ladder*, *Mathsbuddy*, and *Sumdog* (Darragh & Franke, 2021). These online learning platforms are run by private corporations; they are typically of international origin but adapted to the national curriculum. Schools or parents may purchase an annual subscription and there is sufficient content on the platforms to provide mathematics learning for the full year. Although the COVID-19 pandemic exposed inequities of access to internet and digital devices at home (Riwai-Couch et al., 2020), children in Aotearoa New Zealand now have considerable access to devices and the internet at school (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019).

Aotearoa New Zealand was fortunate to avoid the health crisis experienced by many other nations during COVID-19, however the *educational* impact has been widely felt as we had repeated (albeit brief) lockdowns to halt community transmission and children were in and out of school depending on the health alert levels. Given that some parents were desperate to provide extra learning activities for their children during lockdown (RNZ, 2020, 28 July) those companies that provide online instructional programs may have had the opportunity to cement themselves further into the educational landscape; indeed, the marketing of such programs worldwide has ramped up considerably since the pandemic began (Williamson et al., 2020).

To summarise, the context of ILEs and online learning platforms for mathematics instruction can only be understood within the neoliberal policy agenda of education in Aotearoa New Zealand. This agenda includes: the necessity for schools to create their own local curriculum and decide whether to use private providers for part of the mathematics instruction, and the governmental requirement to create ILE spaces with new builds. In the next section I zoom in so that we may examine more closely this particular stage for the learning and teaching of mathematics. As we do this, I invite you to consider your own particular ‘person of interest’. This may be the newly qualified mathematics teacher, the teacher who works in poverty-stricken areas, the ‘out-of-field’ teacher, or the white, middle-class teacher in diverse contexts. Or the person of interest may be the neuro-diverse child, the high achiever, the hearing impaired, the Black girl, the recently arrived immigrant, or the child who engages with schooling to revitalise their indigenous language.¹ As I present the ‘new’ classroom stage for mathematics teaching and learning in Aotearoa New Zealand, I invite you to ponder this question: Can you picture your person in this space?

¹ My apologies here – this list is clearly non-exhaustive and I am aware that I may have missed your particular ‘person of interest’ thus marginalising them further (literally) in this footnote.

The ‘stage’: Innovative learning environments and online mathematics learning

Whilst the ‘theatre’ attends to the broader socio-political context, the ‘stage’ may describe the context at the local level, i.e., the mathematics classroom. There are a number of studies on identity at this level of the ‘zoom lens’ (Lerman, 2001), but most are based in single-cell classrooms, whether they incorporate ‘traditional’ or ‘reform’ instruction (see for example Esmonde, 2009; Heyd-Metzuyanim & Shabtay, 2019; Ma & Singer-Gabella, 2011; Valoyes-Chávez, 2019). In this section I will first describe the ‘new’ stage for learning mathematics – the ILE space and online instructional programs. I follow with an explanation of how students may negotiate the space when learning mathematics and then discuss a couple of features of this ‘new’ stage that set it apart from classrooms of the past.

In a typical ILE environment, children learn in classroom spaces that are designed to fit 40-160 students together with 2-6 teachers (Everatt, Fletcher, & Fickel, 2019). Whilst the teachers are supposed to work collaboratively to teach the entire group, children are required to navigate the space independently. Benade gives an evocative description based on research within Aotearoa New Zealand schools:

The placement of tables and chairs, often boardroom style, is a place where a ‘workshop’ can take place, facilitated by a teacher, or, more appropriately, a ‘learning advisor’ or ‘coach’. A private space off to the side for a small group to work together is a ‘breakout space’. Along with this neoliberal language of the business conference is the imagery of the future hunter-gatherers of the twenty-first century knowledge economy gathering at the ‘campfire’ (a circular formation of Ottomans). Redolent of captivating tales or fellowship, this is a space of gathering together before expedition, or debriefing after. Thirsting for knowledge, some young cubs work intently at a ‘watering hole’, a circular arrangement of seats and tables, where they plan their next project. For those who are required to work on complex tasks (such as numeracy) there are the high tables and chairs that provide a ‘lookout’, allowing these students to gaze intently into the long distance, as they solve challenging problems. (Benade, 2017, p. 802)

Where might we see the teacher in this space? There is little room for the traditional ‘chalk and talk’. The teacher becomes a facilitator - assigning learning activities and managing the learning environment. And at times we may see the teacher engaging with a small group of children (at the “campfire”) and teaching them some mathematics content.

The hunter-gatherer imagery employs a different metaphor to the idea of the stage within a theatre, yet it is scenery that is taken up by a number who write about ILE classrooms. The metaphor comes from Thornburg (e.g., 2004), who also describes the ‘cave’ as being a space for internal reflection, in addition to the more populated learning spaces of waterhole and campfire. In the above scene, the place given to mathematics appears isolated – children at high tables (rather than the low, collaborative spaces) deep in thought as they solve challenging problems. However, mathematics learning may be seen in the other spaces too. Children might be able to engage in small group, collaborative problem solving (at the watering hole) – but we also see many children seated either individually or in pairs and with some kind of digital device (laptop, chromebook, or tablet, for example). What

mathematics learning do these devices provide? In Aotearoa New Zealand it is likely the children will be engaged with commercial platforms that provide individualised learning online (Darragh & Franke, 2021).

Thornburg suggests that each of the neolithic scenes (the campfire, the watering hole and the cave) may be replicated in the online environment. Indeed, one thing missing from Benade’s description above (though he refers to it elsewhere, e.g., Benade, 2015) is the presence of modern technologies in these spaces. As previously discussed, a key aspect of twenty first-century learning and ILE spaces are their “technology-rich” nature. Children and teachers in Aotearoa New Zealand have ready access to computers and hand-held devices and the internet at school (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019), and this makes the use of OMIPs during mathematics somewhat unsurprising. The most popular platform is *Mathletics* (3P Learning, 2021), originally designed in Australia, and subscribed by approximately 40% of the schools in Aotearoa New Zealand that use OMIPs (Darragh & Franke, 2021); there are dozens of other OMIPs to choose from.

The OMIP platforms draw on behaviourist techniques to motivate children to do maths (Jablonka, 2017); for example, completing a number of exercises is rewarded with a game, or the mathematics work is ‘disguised’ in a gaming format. Jablonka (2017) discussed this gamification in the context of OMIP “Sumdog” at a previous Mathematics Education in Society conference. Many of the platforms offer ‘payment’ for doing the mathematics in the form of ‘tokens’, ‘coins’, or ‘points’ that may be spent on designing avatars (or purchasing related paraphernalia) during the reward phase. This is the case for *Mathletics* (3P Learning, 2021): Figure 1 below shows the points, gold bars, and certificates achieved by the depicted (cartoon) ‘learner’. Figure 2 depicts information directed to the teacher – learner analytics, with an example of the type of statistical information given about the learner’s performance and progress.

In general, research within mathematics education is remarkably silent on the use of OMIPs. The plethora of studies into technology use in mathematics tend to focus on issues of teaching and learning (Young, 2017), and they tend to take an uncritical view of the technology itself; greater attention is given to the benefits to learning or the challenges of having teachers adopt the technology. By contrast, outside of mathematics education and particularly in the field of Media Studies we find much critique of the EdTech (educational technology) industry. The aspects of EdTech of concern centre on the personalisation of learning (Roberts-Mahoney, Means, & Garrison, 2016), and ‘big data’ collected via ‘learner analytics’ (Knox, Williamson, & Bayne, 2020). Personalising learning may be argued a valid goal for education but, as pointed out by McRae (2013), the ‘hyper-individualisation’ of the programmes is reductionist (mathematics becomes basic facts, for example) rather than providing personalised learning based on student interest or cultural background. In other words, learning is individualistic and individualised (Biesta, 2012), that is, centered on the *individual learner*, rather than being centred on students as a group. Such an approach does

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not consider the backgrounds and interests of the children as a community of learners in the classroom and thus the teachers' situated knowledge of them is de-valued in this model.

Figure 1: Rewards earned by the *Mathletics* student (3P Learning, 2021) see: <https://www.mathletics.com/nz/features/>

Figure 2: Learner analytics for one student
(3P Learning, 2021) see: <https://www.mathletics.com/nz/features/>

Teaching and learning mathematics on the ‘new’ classroom stage

It may be challenging to see clearly the teaching and learning of mathematics in ILE or OMIP spaces, and so it is perhaps useful to explore how a mathematics ‘lesson’ may proceed. In most Aotearoa New Zealand classrooms, a group rotation is used in mathematics whereby one group works with the teacher and the other groups are assigned other activities. In many schools the groups are ability based (Anthony & Hunter, 2017), despite research critiquing this practice. In some schools, however, groupings are instead fluid, and membership changes according to the needs of the child. In either case, because the class is not taught all together as a whole, communication as to what each student should be doing becomes complex. The illustration below (taken from the embedded video) depicts an “Action Stations” board (see Figure 3). The various activities on offer are represented by pictures and underneath each activity are the names of a group or individual children. The students find their allocated activity, locate the resources they need, and find a space in which to do their task, and often there is the option of ‘free choice activities’ included.

Figure 3: “Action-stations” board: Children find their name and allocated activity (Ministry of Education, 2021) see: <https://www.tki.org.nz/>

Typically, some students are directed to a digital device, and likely an activity on an OMIP such as *Mathletics*. When engaging with mathematics on the OMIP, students might have some choice as to which activity to complete, or they may have been assigned an activity - either by the teacher or by the OMIP’s learning analytics.

(Co-)performing agentic mathematics teacher or learner identities in the ‘new’ mathematics classroom

Returning to the question of your particular person of interest, how do you imagine they co-perform mathematics teacher/learner alongside their other identities on this ‘new’ classroom stage? Might they be agentic in these performances, or would the context constrain how they may *be* a mathematics teacher or learner? To answer these questions, it may help to first look more closely at the way in which the ‘new’ classroom stage may constrain (or enable) particular identity performances, and secondly, consider what the *identity scripts* are that normalise performances on such a stage.

There are a couple of features of the ‘new’ classroom stage that set it apart from classrooms of the past. These may be seen in both the ILE space and the OMIP platforms; *free choice*, and the use of *surveillance*. These two features work to produce the mathematics teacher and learner in particular ways, as discussed below.

Free choice

One notable aspect of the ‘new’ classroom stage is the bodily freedom allowed to students as they perform the learner role. The children in the video certainly seemed in control of their own movement through the classroom space, bodies were not constrained in chairs facing in one direction. The space for being a mathematics learner is considerably expanded; in fact, it even extends beyond the classroom walls, as children may take a device elsewhere or log on to their learning portal at home. Agency for the learner is emphasised in both the ILE environment and the OMIP platforms with this notion of free choice. The school principal speaking in the video linked above mentioned students’ freedom of choice and student agency. The online instructional programs also claim to allow student agency in selecting their own pathways through the available lessons (see *Mathletics* example in Figure 4 below). Within OMIPs, the students’ freedom of choice is further evident in their choice of which game to play or what they might ‘buy’ for their avatar (using the credit points awarded for their mathematics work – see Figure 5).

Figure 4: Choice of learning activities (3P Learning, 2021), see: <https://www.mathletics.com/nz/>

Figure 5: Choosing an avatar (3P Learning, 2021), see: <https://www.mathletics.com/nz/>

Such choice should be understood within neoliberal ideology, where free choice is a key feature of a market model of education. In Figure 5 we see how OMIPs further promote 'marketisation' by producing the mathematics learner as being a consumer in capitalist

society, what Jablonka (2017) calls a ‘token economy’, as students are invited to purchase items for their avatar based on their points ‘earned’ by doing the mathematics work.

Of course, we might question the level to which choices are in fact ‘free’. Whilst children may be able to choose for themselves what to do and how/where to do it, their choices may affect the way in which they are recognised as a learner. Recall Walkerdine’s (1990, 1998) research into mathematics of girls and boys in working-class schools: girls taking on the overt messages about good behaviour and following the rules were seen as hard-working (but not very bright), whereas the boys following the covert messages of exploration were attributed with having ‘real understanding’ and ‘potential’ despite lack of achievement (Walkerdine, 1990). I wonder what might be the overt and covert messages in these ‘free choice’ ILE spaces, and which children might be recognised as normal or pathological due to the messages they follow. Relatedly, Benade (2019) considered whether the ILE space is an inclusive design and identified the challenges faced by those with auditory, sensory and socio-cognitive issues; including the noise, the self-regulation required, anxiety, and getting ‘lost’ in the space. How might such children be recognised as mathematics learners in these cases? Where does your ‘person of interest’ fit here?

The notion of agency when using the OMIPs may certainly be problematised also. The complex learning analytics generate an assessment of students’ next steps for their mathematics learning, and provide activity options based on this assessment (Knox et al., 2020). What appears to be freedom is in fact a tightly constrained choice based on the program’s analysis of required next steps. As cautioned by Lupton & Williamson (2017):

[...] learning analytics platforms appear to displace the embodied expert judgement of the teacher to the disembodied pattern detection of data analytics algorithms [...] A significant risk that children’s opportunities might be narrowed by the assumptions encoded in algorithmic processes is raised by such techniques (p. 787).

In other words, the assessment capability of the OMIPs means that decision-making may be taken out of the teachers’ hands and this power placed with the OMIP instead. This fact constitutes a key area of criticism from the field of Media Studies, as mentioned earlier. Therefore, not only is the child constrained in their choice, but the teacher is de-professionalised (Roberts-Mahoney et al., 2016) through their reduced ability to select their own learning pathways for their students. The mythical free choice in the ‘new’ classroom that appeared to be on the agenda for students is even less evident for teachers. Here we see a further shift in who (or what) is centred on the stage of the mathematics classroom.

In short, the fiction of free choice, promoted by neoliberal ideology, appears to produce agentic performances of mathematics learner or teacher, but this agency is limited and it is controlled - as shall be seen further in the section to follow.

Surveilled performance

Another key feature of the ‘new’ stage of mathematics classrooms is *surveillance*. Researchers in the field have often used Foucault’s (1977/1991) *Discipline and Punish*, applying the “panopticon” to the classroom setting (e.g., Hardy, 2004; Jablonka, 2017; Walshaw, 2010).

Typically, it is the student who is surveilled, but in the modern ILE, full of glass in place of walls, the teacher faces an increased surveillance, their teaching displayed to an extent not possible in the single cell classroom. In the linked video we could spy the teacher in a breakout room behind glass - her mathematics teaching easily visible. The principal in the video used the term “transparency” to describe the teaching practices, conveying a sense of openness both in terms of the physical and the pedagogical. Benade’s (2017) study of teachers’ work in ILE spaces juxtaposes the collaboration and transparency in teacher practice with the “stress of making collaboration work, the feelings of vulnerability, and a sense of always being on show” (p. 803).

The students face a very different kind of surveillance. On the one hand their physical selves may avoid surveillance – they might disappear into a dark corner or beneath a tent – but their learner selves are continually tracked through data collected. Lupton and Williamson (2017) call this “dataveillance”, that is, digital surveillance. In the ILE space, students’ learning and behaviour are firstly tracked via platforms such as Seesaw, ClassDojo, or Google classroom; both teachers and parents can view children’s ‘learning progress’ on these platforms. The OMIPs go further with the sophisticated ‘learning analytics’ as seen earlier in Figure 2, (see also Jablonka, 2017). It is worth noting that this kind of data surveillance forms a violation of an unwritten rule of assessment: that students should know when an activity is being assessed. Pepin and colleagues call this “stealth assessment” (Pepin, Choppin, Ruthven, & Sinclair, 2017), when *everything* the child does is assessed, but they do not necessarily know it. This may be problematic as it denies them the opportunity to knowingly deliver their best effort for the assessed tasks.

What is also important to note here is that a huge amount of data may be collected from children engaging with the OMIP. For example, every keystroke, the length of every pause, the ratio of productive vs unproductive screen time, all may be recorded and used to build up a picture not only of the learner, but also to form a massive database of many thousands of learners.

Performing such analysis depends not just on surveillance of the individual but also on massive dataveillance of millions of data subjects to generate the kinds of big databases from which accurate predictions are made by comparing individuals against norms derived algorithmically from the masses. (Lupton & Williamson, 2017, p. 787)

Ultimately this ‘big data’ (McRae, 2013; Roberts-Mahoney et al., 2016) is used to make the program more addictive, marketable, and profitable. This has been called “colonial design” technology, whereby the providers of the learning platform learn about the learners rather than the learners learning about themselves (Macgilchrist, 2018).

The emphasis on free choice from both the ILE and OMIP spaces also contributes to a form of surveillance. The students are required to be self-managing as they exercise their choices in selecting the activity likely to optimise their learning. For example, students often must manage their own learning to ensure they have completed a list of weekly tasks, and have made progress towards their own individual goals. This kind of self-management is a form of surveillance, whereby the child surveils themselves (see also Jablonka 2017).

“Learning personalization ensures, in this sense, the learner’s individualized and responsabilized investment in their anticipated future self” (Macgilchrist, 2018, p. 242). Being a mathematics learner is about being future-focused via self-management.

Being a mathematics teacher and a mathematics learner therefore includes the performance of self-governance (Foucault, 1991) that results from surveillance. Being a mathematics learner additionally means being datafied, and continually subject to measurement against a norm. To summarise, the stage of the ‘new’ mathematics classroom in Aotearoa New Zealand produces particular identity acts that involve performances of agency, being surveilled, and self-governance. Such acts may be further understood by considering what the identity scripts are that describe normative ways of being the mathematics teacher or learner.

Dominant scripts for identity on the ‘new’ stage

The various identity performances as enabled and normalised on the stage and theatre constitute the *performance scripts*. These are expected or idealised ways of enacting identity that may be taken up by the individual, or ignored/altered via ‘improvisation’. However, I wish to point out that neither the ‘taking up’ of a script nor rejecting it, is an easy (or even available) decision. Scripts, as normative models for identity performance, are powerful and impactful because they privilege a particular way of being. Scripts draw from societal narratives – in this case neoliberal ideology, twenty-first century narratives and the EdTech discourse of educational corporations – which all speak to how one should *be* a learner or a teacher of mathematics. Scripts, whilst produced in wider narratives, are made available in the local context – the classroom stage. On any stage there may be a variety of scripts available for individuals to take up (or there may be very few). Popkewitz’s problem solving child is an example of a script; he shows how for some the desirable script is not available and these learners are “those left behind” (Popkewitz, 2004). In other words, the concept of ‘scripts’ answers the question of how one *should be* - in this case a mathematics teacher or learner in the ‘new’ mathematics classroom. In this section I present two dominant scripts produced in neoliberal and EdTech narratives, which are made available on the ‘new’ classroom stage. We might name these scripts: ‘*twenty-first century mathematics teacher*’ and ‘*twenty-first century mathematics learner*’.

The twenty-first century mathematics teacher

Performing the twenty-first century mathematics teacher means being a coach/guide, being a collaborator, and having an audience (being surveilled). Whilst these performance aspects may be applied to teachers of any subject, they each have implications specifically for the mathematics teacher identity.

The production of the teacher as a coach or guide is evident in OECD texts about the ILE space, where the term “learning professional” (OECD, 2013) may equally be used. Here the teacher is made invisible, in a manner also evident in reform mathematics discourse (Valoyes-Chávez, 2019). Within EdTech discourse they even lose the name ‘teacher’, reduced

instead to ‘coach’, ‘facilitator’, or ‘data-analyst’ (Ideland, 2021). A student-centred emphasis means that the teacher is sidelined; their job is to guide students to their learning, but they are no longer required to teach. Similarly, when using the OMIPs, teachers need only direct students to the computer and then let the program do the teaching – including actual mathematical instruction (some OMIPs have instructional videos for this purpose), assessment, and assigning of tasks. In the case of primary school teachers – who are typically generalists (rather than having a speciality in mathematics teaching) and often described as having a problematic relationship with mathematics (e.g., Boylan & Povey, 2009; Hardy, 2009; Hodgen & Askew, 2011) – the OMIP space encourages them to sidle away from the responsibility for mathematics instruction.

The distancing of teachers from mathematics may be further exacerbated by the notion of teacher as collaborator (Benade, 2017). Collaborations enable teachers to divide out responsibility for various subject areas. In this situation just one of the teachers in the ILE space may take on the mathematics teaching, whilst the others may be responsible for other subject areas instead. Here the reduction of the teacher role goes further; for some, their mathematics teaching services are no longer required at all.

Yet a third aspect of the twenty-first century teacher is somewhat in contrast to the previous two. Whilst the mathematics teaching may be side-lined, the teachers themselves are not at all invisible. As discussed earlier, teachers are visible in a way not typically experienced in a single-cell classroom: their mathematics teaching performance may be observed and judged at any time. Given the literature about primary teacher anxiety regarding mathematics (Hodgen & Askew, 2011; Intawati & Abdurrahman, 2019; Jenßen et al., 2020) this visibility may indeed be intimidating as teachers are forced to put their mathematics teaching on display when they may prefer to avoid it altogether. In this *physical* aspect the contrast between the ILE and the OMIP spaces becomes apparent. In one the mathematics teacher is on show, in the other they are completely hidden. However, *pedagogically* the two spaces generate a similar effect.

The twenty-first century mathematics learner

Performance scripts for the twenty-first century mathematics learner are abundant. This type of learner is produced globally in OECD texts (e.g., OECD, 2013) and produced locally in Ministry of Education documents, for example:

New Zealand needs an education system that provides its people with the skills and knowledge they require to be successful in life and in an increasingly global economy. An effective education system provides qualifications that open doors to future opportunities and the skills needed in today’s society and the modern workplace. Equipping learners for a digitally enabled future is a key goal of our Four Year Plan. Demand for future-focused learning is increasing – the Ministry’s ICT strategy and our twenty-first century practice in teaching and learning priority ensure we have the right focus to meet this need. (Ministry of Education, 2016, p. 10)

The discursive emphasis is very clear in this excerpt that prioritises “success” in a “global economy” and ties together “future-focused learning” with digital skills. The twenty-first

century learner is also produced in EdTech discourse, and marketed via the OMIP websites (Darragh, 2020). As Macgilchrist explains, to be successful in the twenty-first century, according to the mainstream argument, requires the “skills of creativity, collaboration, critique, and communication [...] This type of success is thoroughly entangled with the neoliberal, self-optimizing, ‘entrepreneurial self’” (Macgilchrist, 2018, p. 242). Accordingly, I argue that performing the twenty-first century mathematics learner means to be entrepreneurial, self-managing, and individual.

Both the ILE space and OMIP platforms position the mathematics learner as a *self-managing entrepreneur*. If the 20th century classroom was designed to produce factory workers then the ILE space clearly prepares for a very different workplace, one that likely matches up with our mental images of the Google offices - themselves having become something of a trope. The entrepreneur is also produced in the OMIP platforms as children are encouraged to engage in the capitalist behaviour of buying products for their avatars. The twenty-first century mathematics learner is self-managing; they must meet their own learning goals and manage not only their own behaviour but also take responsibility for their own learning. It was notable that the Action Station task board in the video contained pictures to direct children to learning tasks, meaning that even children who cannot yet read are responsible for their own learning. The OMIPs encourage the children in this self-management, offering rewards for those who engage in large quantities of activities.

Finally, the twenty-first century mathematics learner is an *individual*, as made explicit in the hyper-personalised learning emphasised on both ILE and OMIP spaces. The ethos of twenty first-century education is very much student-centered (OECD, 2013), and we could certainly see this in the video linked earlier. The field of mathematics education has long been a proponent of ‘reform’ mathematics, with a de-emphasis on teacher-centred, traditional practices. However, there are some differences between the student-centred, problem-solving reform mathematics class (see also Lundin, 2012; Popkewitz & Lindblad, 2004) and the student-centred, individualised learning promoted by neoliberal ideology. The OMIPs and ILEs are firmly situated within the neoliberal version of ‘personalised learning’ (Darragh, 2020). Learning within this ideology entails receiving a separate and individualised learning plan – a task much more achievable by the artificial intelligence of learning analytics (and making the teacher ever more irrelevant). Further, there is a competitive aspect to this script; competition in games becomes competition for jobs in the future workplace.

To summarise, the twenty-first century teacher and learner are scripts produced by the neoliberal theatre, on the ‘new’ student- or device-centred classroom stage, and in the narratives of EdTech and educational policy documents. However, I wish to reiterate that performing mathematics teacher or learner is not about the exact following of a script. The script forms a notion of the ideal mathematics teacher or learner, against which an identity performance might be measured, recognised, or found lacking. Whilst any individual’s performance of mathematics teacher or learner identity is formed at least in part by the available scripts, following the script is not always equally available for all people, and divergences from the script may be differently recognised depending on the person also. In

this co-performance of identity emerges issues of intersectionality (Bullock, 2017; Leyva, 2016, 2017) and where we may see the impact of the power of recognition (or ‘recognition power’). Therefore, scripts are problematic in a number of ways: firstly, because they are not equally available to all, secondly, because improvisation from the script may be seen as pathological, and finally, scripts narrow the possibilities for ways of being.

Improvising the mathematics teacher or learner?

The scripts for mathematics teacher and learner seem inevitable given the neoliberal theatre of education, and the ‘new’ classroom stage that emulates the twenty-first century workplace. However, considering identity as performative, we might ask what divergence from these scripts are even possible. Butler’s notion of the repetition of acts allows a certain agency here. Each time we perform mathematics teacher or mathematics learner we may renew the performance differently – we may improvise. It is precisely in the repetition of identity that an individual may revise the act, and any act may follow scripts closely or deviate. While performances are always constrained by the context, there is a whisper of agency here; the possibility of revision raises the question of what the alternative ways of being a mathematics teacher or learner are. Already we see alternatives to the mathematics teacher script; it may be sidestepped via collaboration with other teachers, or the use of online programs enable teachers to avoid the role completely. What of the mathematics learner? Is there a way to be a mathematics learner that denies the self-managing, independent entrepreneur? What sort of mathematics learner would this improvisation produce? And, finally, how might the improvisation be recognised?

To conclude, performative identity as a stylised repetition of acts means that we need to take seriously the physical, temporal, and ideological space in which these acts are made. A mathematics teacher or learner identity is made, renewed, and revised in every individual performance of ‘teacher’ or ‘learner’. In this paper, I have shown how ILE classroom design and online mathematics platforms dictate certain behaviours for mathematics teaching and learning and make available scripts for the normal (twenty-first century) mathematics teacher/learner. A few questions remain, and I ask the reader to once again consider their person of interest. For whom are these scripts more available? How might improvisation away from the script be recognised? Finally, what alternative ways of being a mathematics teacher or learner are imaginable beyond these scripts?

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